

Real-time Object Detection Using Tensorflow

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Abstract— Object detection using Tensorflow can be a valuable tool in an online exam portal. By utilizing object detection, the system can detect and prevent cheating attempts during an exam, as well as ensure that students are present and engaged throughout the exam. It is a challenging task in computer vision that involves identifying and localizing objects within a video. This seminar paper presents an analysis of objects visible on the screen and provides a powerful set of tools for developing and deploying deep learning models. The model is trained and numerous test cases are implemented in the Tensorflow environment which provides a set of pre-built CNNs that can be used for object detection.

Keywords— Object Detection, Convolutional Neural Network(CNNs), Object class labels, Tensorflow ,COCO-SSD

I. INTRODUCTION

Online exam portals are one of the uses for TensorFlow's real-time object identification technology. In online exams, it is crucial to ensure the integrity of the exam process and prevent cheating. Object detection using Tensorflow can help achieve this goal by automatically detecting and flagging suspicious activities during an exam. Deep learning approaches have made significant progress in recent years in terms of increasing the precision and speed of object detection systems. TensorFlow, a Google-developed open-source software library, is one of the most widely used deep learning frameworks for object detection. The concept of object detection, several ways taken to address this issue, and the difficulties associated with real-time object identification are introduced at the outset of the study. This includes discussing the various forms of cheating that object detection can catch, like the usage of mobile devices, impersonation etc. Additionally, the model's underlying architecture is covered, including the Single Shot MultiBox Detector (SSD) algorithm and convolutional neural networks (CNNs).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Priyal Jawale, Hitiksha Patel Chaudhary, and Niveditha Rajput in [1] This research paper that proposes a real-time object detection system using Tensorflow, a popular open-source machine learning library. TensorFlow's Object Detection API, which offers pre-trained models for various object detection tasks, is used in the proposed solution. On their dataset, which contains images of various objects in a range of backgrounds and lighting conditions, the authors refined the pre-trained models. The suggested system's various parts, such as picture preprocessing, object detection,

and result visualization, are thoroughly explained in the paper. The system's performance in terms of precision, speed, and computing complexity is also covered by the authors.

R. K. Singh and K. Singh in [2]. This study suggests a single-shot detector (SSD) algorithm and MobileNetV2 neural network architecture for a real-time item detection system. The authors want to create a real-time object detection system that can function on embedded systems or other low-power gadgets like cellphones. They accomplish this using the MobileNetV2 neural network architecture, a mobile device-specific neural network that is compact and effective. The Single-Shot Detector (SSD) technique, which detects objects with a single forward pass of the neural network, is also used by the authors. In comparison to other object detection techniques that call for multiple passes through the neural network, this strategy increases the system's effectiveness and speed. The authors ran tests on the COCO dataset, a sizable object detection dataset with 80 object categories, to gauge how well their system performed. On the COCO dataset, the authors report a mean average precision (mAP) of 71.7% at a CPU speed of up to 40 frames per second. The effectiveness of other cutting-edge object identification methods, like YOLOv3 and Faster R-CNN, was also evaluated by the authors. According to the findings, their method was more effective while still achieving comparable accuracy, making it appropriate for real-time object identification applications on low-power gadgets.

A. Javed et al. in [3] This research paper that presents a real-time cheating detection system in online exams using object detection and face recognition techniques. The authors want to create a system that can spot attempts at cheating during online exams in real time. They accomplish this by employing object detection techniques to find cheating tools like cell phones, smartwatches, and papers. In order to identify the student taking the exam and make sure that no unauthorised individual is taking their place, they also use face recognition technology. The suggested method employs a facial recognition model based on the VGG16 architecture to identify the student's face and a Faster R-CNN object detection model to find cheating assistance. On their unique dataset, which contains pictures of students and typical cheating tools, the authors trained both models.

M. Z. Akram et al. in [4] This research paper that presents a comprehensive survey of various real-time object detection

techniques. In addition to highlighting the salient characteristics and practical uses of various methodologies, the authors hope to provide an overview of recent developments and difficulties in this area. The first part of the paper discusses the idea of real-time object detection and some of its uses in robotics, autonomous vehicles, and surveillance. The difficulties and constraints of real-time object detection are then covered by the authors, including the necessity for high accuracy, quick processing, and minimal computer complexity. The following section of the study offers a thorough analysis of various real-time object recognition approaches based on both conventional computer vision techniques and deep learning techniques. Viola-Jones, HOG, and SIFT are examples of conventional techniques, while YOLO, SSD, Faster R-CNN, and Mask R-CNN are examples of deep learning-based techniques. The fundamental characteristics that qualify each method for use in real-time applications are highlighted by the authors, who also explain the benefits and drawbacks of each technique. Additionally, they offer a comparison of how various methods performed on well-known datasets like COCO and PASCAL VOC.

Z. Wu and Z. Zhou's in [5]. This research proposes an innovative method for detecting cheating in online exams in real-time using object identification techniques. The use of mobile devices, unauthorised access to study materials, and impersonation are just a few examples of cheating behaviours that the authors identify and categorise using TensorFlow and the YOLO (You Only Look Once) algorithm. The authors claim that their method of real-time cheating behaviour detection is above 95% accurate.

III. METHODOLOGY

Our approach is a real-time object detection using tensorflow in online exam portal to avoid malpractices. Using a pre-trained model, real-time object identification using TensorFlow identifies things in real-time video streams or photos. A frame of an image or video is input into the model, which then processes it through a number of convolutional layers to extract its features. The identification of objects in the image and their corresponding positions is then accomplished using these attributes. The pre-trained models of TensorFlow can recognise a variety of items, including people, vehicles, animals, and even specialised objects like logos or traffic signs. The models are extremely versatile and adaptable to different object identification tasks since they may be trained to detect certain objects or classes of objects. In the context of online exam portals, TensorFlow may be used to identify exam-cheating practices like using a mobile device.

The implementation of real-time object detection using Tensorflow involves the use of deep learning algorithms to detect objects in real-time. Images or videos of the scene or object are first recorded, and these are then fed into a neural network model that has already been trained. The video is processed by the neural network, which also recognises the items that are visible. Although the neural network architecture for real-time object detection can vary, models like Single-Shot Detector (SSD) and You Only Look Once (YOLO) are frequently employed. These models can recognise things quickly and accurately because they are trained on vast quantities of picture data. Boxes are displayed

under the objects to show their location after the neural network has determined which ones are present in the scene or image. Numerous applications, including self-driving cars, surveillance systems, and online tests, can make use of this information. In the context of an online exam portal, the function of real-time object detection using TensorFlow can be used to detect cheating attempts by students. The system captures images or videos of the students taking the exam and processes them using the object detection model. If any unauthorized objects, such as mobile phones or notes, are detected.

Basic CNN Components

A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a type of neural network commonly used for image recognition and classification tasks. The basic components of a CNN include:

Convolutional Layer: CNN's goal is to discover feature representations of the inputs. Several feature maps are present in the convolutional layer, which is the first layer from which characteristics are derived. Local traits of various places in the previous layer are extracted using each neuron of the same feature map. The input feature maps are first convolved with a learnt kernel (mask) in order to produce a new feature, and the outcomes are then fed into a nonlinear activation function. By using several filter masks, we will obtain various feature maps. Softmax, sigmoid, tanh, and Relu are the typical activation functions.

Pooling Layer: The pooling layer of a CNN can be used for secondary feature extraction. The feature maps' dimensions are fundamentally decreased, and feature extraction is made more robust. The size of the feature maps in the pooling layer is dictated by the movement step of the masks and is typically put between two convolutional layers. also known as a "stride of masks." Average pooling and maximum pooling are the two main pooling strategies. By stacking many Convolutional layers and pooling layers, we may additionally extract the high-level properties of inputs.

Fully Connected Layer: Our matrix is vectorized, flattened, and sent into the fully linked layer. All of the neurons from the layer above are coupled to every single neuron in the layer below it in a completely connected layer. The fully connected layers don't retain any spatial information. The final fully connected layer is followed by an output layer. We can see the full neural network once all the neurons have been combined. Softmax regression is frequently used for classification problems since it produces an accurate probability distribution of the outputs to categorise as dog, cat, automobile, truck, etc.

CNN Architecture

Object Class Labels

The various categories or classes of objects that the model is trained to recognise are referred to as object class labels in real-time object detection using TensorFlow. The objects that the model has detected are identified and labelled using these labels. For instance, a model that is taught to recognise items in photographs may be trained on a dataset that contains pictures of vehicles, people, objects, animals, and more. When a new image is fed into the model, it will be trained to recognise the features of the various objects and label them appropriately. This will enable it to recognise and label the objects in the image. TensorFlow commonly uses integer values to represent object class labels, with each integer standing for a different class label. The predicted class label and confidence score or probability for each detected object are often included in the model output for object detection. Object class labels are a crucial part of the system in real-time object detection using TensorFlow in Angular because they enable the system to precisely identify and label the objects identified in real-time. The system can then employ this data for a number of purposes, including object tracking and security monitoring.

Figure 2: Landmark detection with deep learning

Figure 2: Visualizing Landmark recognition using machine learning

Figure 1: object class labels are used to label and identify key attributes in an image

To detect the objects with class label involves various steps:

1. A webcam component is built to take real-time video input. The processed video frames are then subjected to object identification and classification using TensorFlow.js, with the objects being recognised by their class labels. Applying a trained model to the incoming video frames is the object detection procedure. This model has gained the ability to identify objects from various classes after being trained on a sizable dataset of photos. The model creates predicted boxes under the objects and labels them as it processes the incoming video frames.

2. The next step involves rendering the output of the object detection process on the video frames in real-time. On the video frames are displayed the class labels and predict for each object. The user can then engage with the objects that have labels in a variety of ways, for as by clicking on them to get further details.

Detecting Class labels with CNNs, Tensorflow, SSD

```
import { AfterViewInit, Component, ElementRef, OnInit, ViewChild } from '@angular/core';
import * as cocoSsd from '@tensorflow-models/coco-ssd';
import '@tensorflow/tfjs';
```

The necessary libraries and Angular components are imported using the import statements. The Angular components AfterViewInit, Component, ElementRef, and ViewChild are used to provide the behaviour and layout of the Angular component. TensorFlow.js's core library is @tensorflow/tfjs, while the COCO-SSD object identification model is provided by the cocoSsd package.

```
@ViewChild('video')
public video!: ElementRef;
error: any;
predictionValue=[{
  class: '---',
  score: 0
}];
totalObjectsDetected=0;
dataLoading=false;
```

To obtain a reference to the video HTML element in the component template, use the @ViewChild decorator. The video element from the component class can now be accessed and modified by the component. The projected class and score for the identified object are stored in an array called predictionValue. The total number of items detected will be tracked using the variable totalObjectsDetected. When the model is loading, the boolean value dataLoading will be used to display a loading spinner.

```

async ngOnInit(){
  this;
}
async ngAfterViewInit(){
  await this.setupDevices();
  await this.loadImageDetection();
}
async setupDevices() {
  if (navigator.mediaDevices && navigator.mediaDevices.getUserMedia) {
    try {
      const stream = await navigator.mediaDevices.getUserMedia({
        video: true
      });
      if (stream) {
        this.video.nativeElement.srcObject = stream;
        this.video.nativeElement.play();
        this.error = null;
      } else {
        this.error = "You have no output video device";
      }
    } catch (e) {
      this.error = e;
    }
  }
}
}

```

Using the `getUserMedia()` method, this code tries to request permission to access the user's camera. If it is successful, a `MediaStream` object representing the camera's stream of video data is returned. Before proceeding on to the next line of code, the `await` keyword is used to wait for the `getUserMedia()` method to resolve.

Next it plays the video element if `getUserMedia()` successfully returns a stream and sets the video element's `srcObject` property to the stream object. The error property of the component is set to a message stating that no output video device is available if there is no stream object. Then it sets the component's error property to the error message if an error arises when attempting to access the camera (for instance, if the user refuses permission to view the camera).

```

async loadImageDetection() {
  this.dataLoading = true;
  cocoSsd.load().then(model => {
    model.detect(this.video.nativeElement).then(predictions => {
      this.predictionValue = predictions;
      this.totalObjectsDetected = predictions.length;
      this.dataLoading = false;
      this.loadImageDetection();
    });
  });
}
}

```

These lines implements the asynchronous method `loadImageDetection()`, which loads a pre-trained model from the COCO-SSD (Common Objects in Context - Single Shot Detector) dataset and then conducts object detection on the camera's video stream.. Using the `load()` method made available by the `cocoSsd` module, it loads the COCO-SSD model. The returned model object is handled by the `then()` method. By invoking the `detect()` function of the loaded model object, it detects objects in the video stream. The array of predicted objects and their confidence ratings are returned by the `detect()` method, which accepts a video element as an input. The `then()` method is used to handle the predictions after they are returned and to update the component's properties with the outcomes of object detection. The array of predicted objects returned by the `detect()` method is set as the component's `predictionValue` . The size of the predictions

array is likewise set for the `totalObjectsDetected` attribute. The `dataLoading` attribute is then set to `false`, indicating that object detection is now complete.

In general, a pre-trained model from the COCO-SSD dataset is loaded and used to perform real-time object detection on a video stream from the user's camera.

IV. CONCLUSION

A useful technology that lets developers create applications that can identify and recognise items in real-time is real-time object detection using TensorFlow. Developers can take advantage of the capabilities of machine learning to identify objects in a video stream from a user's camera by employing a pre-trained deep learning model like COCO-SSD. The `@tensorflow/tfjs` package, which offers a set of APIs to load pre-trained models and carry out object identification, is used in this procedure. Additionally, we make use of the `@tensorflow-models/coco-ssd` library, which has a trained object detection model for images and videos. We can quickly load the pre-trained model and use it to find objects in real-time video streams with the help of these libraries. We need to add a video element to our template and use the `ViewChild` decorator to obtain a reference in order to achieve real-time object identification in Angular. Then, we can gain access to the user's camera and stream the video using the `navigator.mediaDevices.getUserMedia()` method. Once we have the video stream, we can use the pre-trained model's `detect()` method to quickly identify objects. The ability to construct a variety of applications, from security systems to autonomous vehicles, utilising real-time object detection with TensorFlow in Angular is a strong strategy. We can develop programmes that can detect and identify things with a high degree of accuracy in real-time by utilising the power of machine learning.

REFERENCES

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